

THE ROLE OF VULGAR WORDS IN POETIC SPEECH

Khusanova Marifat Ahmadjonovna

Teacher of Ferghana State University, doctor
of philosophy (PhD) in philological sciences

xusanovamarifat84@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8004754>

ANNOTATION

This article discusses the use of vulgarisms, which are one of the lexical units belonging to the non-literary layer, in order to ensure the artistry of speech.

Key words: poetic speech, vulgarism, expressiveness, individual style, creative skill, connotative meaning, humor.

In linguistics, a number of expressions such as extremely negative attitude, disdain, discrimination, and insult are clearly visible in insulting words called vulgarisms. That is why we usually consider such words as a unit that does not correspond to the norms of the literary language. Vulgar words live in speech not according to their nominative meaning, but according to their connotative meaning. Insults are used in works of art, mainly in the speech of characters. In the process of linguistic analysis, it will be possible to group the vulgarisms introduced into the artistic work according to whose speech (gender, social class, position, age, etc.) they are used, in what situations and for what reason they are used, as well as their lexical-semantic structure, characteristic of the dialect, etc. In poetic speech, vulgarisms are sometimes observed in the language of the lyrical hero. In this, vulgarisms are used for various purposes, including:

1. Эшик қоқиб турар гадодек,
Топганингни бергин-да, кузат.
У суллоҳга ён бериб қўйма,
Жаҳаннам у, туби йўқ ғафлат.
2. Бунда бари чала қолди,
Қозон қайнар қопқоқсиз.
Ҳар **бетаффиқ** чўмич солар,
Овқатим пишар тузсиз.
3. **Бетаффиқ** ота бир кун
Келди-ю йўл бошлади.
Гўдақларин арранинг

Бир ёнига ташлади.

In this place, the negative attitude of the speaker towards the object is vividly expressed and expressiveness is ensured through the high negative tone in the semantic content of the taboos *sulloh* (*а. ўтакетган хира, сурбет, шилқим*)¹, *бетаффиқ* (*1. имони йўқ, муртад; 2. Номуси йўқ, уятсиз*)²

¹ Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. III жилд. "ЎЗМЭ" Тошкент, 2007. –Б. 585.

² Ўша луғат. –Б. 238.

In poetic works, as well as in prose works, vulgar words are used in the speech of heroes to reflect their individual characteristics, for example, they are used to show the negative character and immorality of the hero:

– Сенга нима, **қизталоқ**,
Сенга ўтин керакмас!
Сен ёлғизсан, сенга не,
Барибир олов етмас.

Sometimes, in order to express the artistic goal of the creator, vulgarism can be used not with a negative denotative meaning, but with a certain degree of humor, to express a positive meaning, to cause a light caress or laughter:

1. Чол ўзида йўқ хурсанд,
Йўл – азобдан қутулди.
Лек босди уни бир йў:
...Буёғи қандай бўлар.
Ахир шунча йўл ҳамдам...
Овсарроқ бўлса бўлар!
Таклиф этди йигитни
Бир пиёла яхнага.

2. Бугун ҳам
яшадим беҳуда,
Шу қурғур
омадга ишониб.
Жодугар
илинжлар домида
Гоҳ йиғлаб, гоҳида юпаниб.

Not negativity in the meaning expressed in the lexemes of овсар (*ган англамайдиган, эси пастроқ*)³ **қурғур** (*енгил сўкиш: қурмағур, тушмагур*) prevailed. In this way, the vulgar word was manifested with a unique aesthetic appeal by the artist's skill.

Therefore, in poetic works, words with a limited scope of use, especially vulgar words, are used, and they are important in ensuring that the work is effective, fluent, and close to the vernacular. At the same time, such words are used in the language of lyrical heroes and characters, helping to fully express the speaker's thoughts and the situation shown through speech.

We can say that the words with a limited scope of consumption, considered in the example of Farida Afro'z's poetic works, can serve to individualize the artist's style, increase the expressiveness of the speech, and further expand the possibilities of the artistic style.

³ Ўзбек тилининг изоҳли луғати. V жилдик. “ЎзМЭ” – Тошкент, 2007. III жилд. –Б. 81.

References:

- 1.Rasulova, Azizaxon Muydinovna; Xusanova Ma'rifat Axmadjonovna. POETIC NUTQDA SINONIMLARDAN FOYDALANISH MAHORATI. ORIENTAL RENAISSANCE: INNOVATIVE, EDUCATIONAL, NATIONAL AND SOCIAL SCIENCES. ORIENS_Volume 2_ISSUE 10- 2. 2022 807-811. (Rasulova, Azizakhon Muydinovna; Khusanova Marifat Akhmadjonovna. THE SKILL OF USING SYNONYMS IN POETIC SPEECH. ORIENTAL RENAISSANCE: INNOVATIVE, EDUCATIONAL, NATIONAL AND SOCIAL SCIENCES. ORIENS_Volume 2_ISSUE 10-2.2022 807-811).
- 3.KHUSANOVA M & KHUSANOVA M. ROLE OF OCCASSIONAL UNITS IN FARIDA AFRUZ'S IDIOSTYLE. Thematics Journal of Education Impact Factor (UIF-2020):7.528 Impact Factor (IFS-2020):7.433: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6467338>, P-63-69 12.04.2022.
- 4.Xusanova, M.A. The use of archaism in the works of Farida Afroz. International Scientific Journal ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science Philadelphia, USA issue 04, volume 96 published April 20, 2021. So: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1TAS-04-96-51> Doi <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS> Scopus ASCC:1208.
- 5.Xusanova, M.A. The use of expressive phonetic means in Farida Afroz's works. International Scientific Journal ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science Philadelphia, USA issue 09, volume 101, published September 28, 2021.Soi: <http://s-o-i.org/1.1TAS-09-101-81> Doi <https://dx.doi.org/10.15863/TAS> ScopusASCC:1200.
6. Ma'rifat Axmadjonovna Xusanova. Individual – stilistik neologizmlardan foydalanish – uslubiy o'ziga xoslik belgisi (Farida Afro'z she'rlari misolida) International Scientific Conference "RESENT RESEARCHES IN THE MODERN WORLD". 26-27.05.2016. Выпуск 5(13) Часть 1. – С. 125-130.
- 7.A.Rasulova THE STUDING BARRIER CONNECTION IN THE WORLD LINGUISTICS. Thematic journal of Education, 2022, 38-42.
- 8.A.Rasulova, M.Xalilova МИКРОМАТНЛАРГА НУТҚ СИСТЕМАСИ СИФАТИДА ЁНДАШУВ. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2022, 197-203.
- 9.A.Rasulova Linguistic Features Of The Conditional Field In Uzbek Language. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations, 2021,104-110.
- 10.Афрўз Фарида (Бўтаева). "Ўша кун - бугундир". Сайланма. Тошкент.: "Шарқ", 2013. – Б. 383.
- 11.Nuritdinova Rayxona Numonovna, Shodiyeva Asila CRIMINAL LEXICON AND ITS REPRESENTATION
- 12.<https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbss/article/view/2430/2095>
- 13.R Nuritdinova, R. N.(2021). Ideas that led to the emergence of sociolinguistics and interpretation of the study. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. 11 (3), 1440-1442
- 14.Nuritdinova, R., & Kurbonova, M. (2022). REPRESENTATION OF OCCASIONAL UNITS IN SOCIOLECTS.Thematics Journal of Education,7(2).
- 15.Nuritdinova R. N. (2022) Ijtimoiy dialetklar. "Ilm-zakovatimiz – senga, ona-Vatan!" mavzusidagi Respublika onlayn ilmiy-amaliy anjuman materiallari. 66- 68. FarDU
- 16.Seitova Z. P. (2023). ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY AS AN IMPORTANT DIRECTION OF REFORMS IN MODERN UZBEKISTAN. Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research, 3(12), 275–284. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/D6MPB>

- 17.СЕЙТОВА, З. (2022, April). РАВЕНСТВО МУЖЧИН И ЖЕНЩИН-ОДНО ИЗ ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ РАЗВИТИЯ ОБЩЕСТВА. In E Conference Zone (pp. 78-80).
- 18.Seitova, Z. P. (2022). Women of the Aral Sea Region: A New Approach, Problems and Their Solutions. International Journal of Social Science Research and Review, 5(4), 62-66.
- 19.Seitova, Z. P. (2022). Features of the Social Status of Women in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding, 9(2), 407-411
- 20.Kodirov, O. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF CONNECTION CREATING ART WORKS IN INTERDISCIPLINARY. Science and innovation 2 (B2), 373-375
- 21.Safarovich, Q. O. (2022). TEENAGER CHILD PSYCHOLOGY. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 10 (5), 454-462
- 22.Safarovich, Q. O. (2023). МАКТАБ YOSHIDAGI O'QUVCHILARNI MA'NAVIY SHAKLLANISHIDA PSIXOLOGLARNING O'RNI. O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI 2 (15), 156-161
- 23.Safarovich, Q. O. (2023). TARBIIYASI QIYIN O'QUVCHILARNING XULQ-ATVORI BILAN BOG'LIQ MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISH MASALALARI. PEDAGOG 6 (2), 367-371

